

DRUGS & FINE CHEMICALS

Hoffmann-La Roche, Inc., is reducing the price of ascorbic acid from \$4.10 to \$3.85 per kilo, effective today (November 6). The company feels the action is appropriate under price control regulations and is in the process of filing the price reduction with the Price Commission. Roche says the current price, now being reduced, was established January 5, 1972, pursuant to specific Price Commission approval. There have been no other price increases in any Roche products since the price freeze in August 1971, a company spokesman adds.

Ascorbic acid supplies have eased a bit, although sources say there may still be shortages on certain types of the vitamin. Producers are currently seeking to improve their inventory position after the heavy demand of last year and earlier this year. Output of ascorbic last year (US output plus imports) ran to nearly 18 million pounds and demand has been growing at better than 6 percent annually in recent years.

Choline chloride is reported moving well at this point, although there was some weakening in prices for feed grade solution at mid-year due to accumulation of inventory and a downturn in the export market. Feed grade material made up by far the bulk of last year's 46.6-million-pound production of choline chloride.

Output through the first eight months of 1972 was running slightly ahead of the same period for last year and indicates a probable total for the year of about 50 million pounds.

Citric acid demand continues to grow for established uses and some new industrial applications are reported under evaluation. Should these applications take hold it's likely new capacity will be needed. Another good increase of food acidulant use of citric acid is projected for 1973.

Elsewhere in drug and fine chemical markets, suppliers of quinines and quinine continue to have different ideas about pricing. Prices for replacement stocks, scheduled to arrive later this month, are likely to reflect the higher costs of European processors of cinchona alkaloids.

Bismuths are quiet after the upward price adjustments made in mid-October to reflect a 50-cent increase in bismuth metal on October 1. An initial advance in nitrate to \$4.08 in 100-pound drums settled back to \$4.02 a pound due to competitive influences.

Use of bismuths has declined over the years, but still accounts for over a million pounds of bismuth metal use annually. Most recent Bureau of Mines figures indicate 1,183,035 pounds of bismuth metal went to pharmaceutical application in 1970 as against 1,250,539 pounds in the previous year.

Ascorbic Acid—Producers say the supply situation has eased somewhat, although there may still be shortages on certain types of ascorbic. However, plants are probably still operating full as producers seek to improve their inventory position after the heavy demand of last year and earlier this year.

Full production is expected by the end of the year from a new Roche plant with capacity of about 17 million pounds annually. Addition of this plant would double current estimated industry capacity.

Tariff Commission has, at times, indicated domestic production of ascorbic acid in excess of 1 million pounds per month, or a practical production capacity of around 12 million pounds annually. In addition, the US has become a net importer in recent years as imports have been running at the rate of about 6 million pounds per year.

Some 55 to 60 percent of ascorbic acid demand is for use in pharmaceutical preparations, while about 40 percent goes to food and beverage use and about 3 percent for export.

Observers say pharmaceutical demand has fallen somewhat short of expectations in 1972. A surge in demand for 250 and 500 milligram tablets for use in treatment of colds has peaked out. This demand, on top of normal requirements for the pharmaceutical trade and for food and other uses, had producers literally, running production facilities three shifts and seven days a week.

What the daily human requirement for ascorbic acid is remains open to question, but advocates in recent years, most notably Dr. Linus Pauling, have suggested that it is many times the amount needed just to prevent scurvy.

Actually, food fortification uses are said to have grown at a much faster annual rate than pharmaceutical use over

THE WEEK'S PRICE CHANGES

Ending November 3, 1972

ADVANCED		REDUCED	
Silver cyanide, 2.5c. per oz.		None	
nitrate, 1.6c. per oz.			
COMPARATIVE PRICE INDEXES (100=1959 average)			
Last Week	Prev. Week	Last Month	Nov. 5, 1971
80.85	80.85	80.83	80.73

For Current Prices See Page 38

the long term and it's expected that this will continue to be the case.

A 5 percent annual growth rate projected for ascorbic, is considered a bit low by some sources in the market. It's pointed out that the historical rate over the decade of the 1960's was in excess of 6 percent per year.

Choline Chloride—Output of choline chloride amounted to 32,930,000 pounds during the first eight months of the year, up from 31,283,000 pounds during the January-August period last year.

Total production of 46,599,000 pounds in 1971 compares with 18,687,000 pounds ten years previous, indicating an average annual growth rate in the market of about 9.6 percent over the past decade.

Bulk of use remains in the feed trade, but some pharmaceutical and "technical" choline chloride is also produced. In addition, other compounds—choline bitartrate, choline dihydrogen citrate and tricholine citrate—are offered.

Production of these other compounds, although not currently reported, is believed to be very small compared to the feed grade material. Tariff Commission last reported production of choline bitartrate amounting to 208,000 pounds in 1964, while output of choline dihydrogen citrate in that year was 71,000 pounds. Other choline salts, including medicinal grade chloride, probably amounted to less than 100,000 pounds.

Feed grade material is used largely as an additive to poultry and swine feeds. Use in beef and dairy cattle feeds has not developed as had been hoped. Pharmaceutical cholines are classified as gastrointestinal agents and wind up in a wide range of combination preparations, often with various B-complex vitamins and methionine.

Feed grade choline chloride (70 percent aqueous solution) in tankcars is reported at 12¼c. per pound, delivered East. Truckload lots of 30,000 pounds in drums are 12½c. per pound, same basis. These prices are down ¼c per pound from last report.

Fifty percent choline chloride, dry supplement, in carload lots of 50,000 pounds is reported at 12c. per pound and truckload lots of 30,000 pounds are 12½c. per pound, unchanged from last report.

A domestic producer of choline bitartrate and choline dihydrogen citrate lists prices for the materials at \$1.50 a pound in 100-pound drums, delivered. Less than 100-pound lots are \$1.65 a pound, but quantities of 500 pounds or more are available at \$1.35 a pound. Tricholine citrate (65 percent solution) lists at \$1.35 a pound.

Imports of these materials are reported at prices ranging from 90c. to \$1.30 a pound, depending on the compound and the quantity involved.

Feed grade volume has held up fairly well this year, although there was some earlier report of accumulating inventories and a drop in inquiries for material for export. It's believed less than 10 percent of material goes to the export market, however.

Citric Acid—The food acidulant market has shown good growth this year and the outlook for 1973 is for another increase as some business is shifted away from fumaric acid.

Citric remains by far the largest volume acidulant used, accounting for over half a total market estimated at more than 150 million pounds annually with a value of \$35 million to \$40 million.

Most recently, citric and derivatives

EM is basic in Alkaloids

Who

• Or industrial, pharma

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EM Labor

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URIC

Report From Europe
Rhone-Progil SA
Reaches a Status
Amid Top Twenty

In Rhone-Progil SA, France has for the first time a purely chemicals company in the Top Twenty. The largest of the Rhone-Poulenc daughter companies, it is not yet in the same league as E. I. duPont de Nemours & Co., Union Carbide Corporation, Imperial Chemical Industries, Ltd., or the German "Big

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Pesticide Advertising Alleged To Make False Safety Claims In Latest Crackdown by FTC

Federal Trade Commission has begun a crackdown on what it calls "misleading" pesticide advertising on television and

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Denver, Colorado 80217

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